

IMPACT OF RELATIONSHIP WITH TEACHERS, CAMPUS FACILITIES AND PERSONAL GROWTH ON HAPPINESS OF STUDENTS AT CAMPUS.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of teacher-student relationships, campus climate, and personal growth on student happiness in higher education. A descriptive research design with a sample size of 100 students, Primary data was collected Through questionnaire and was analysed by applying regression analysis, Anova, and correlation analysis. Results show strong correlations between happiness and relationships ($r = 0.9071$), campus climate ($r = 0.9036$), and personal growth ($r = 0.9320$). Gender does not significantly impact happiness ($p = 0.4954$). Findings suggest that improving teacher relationships, campus facilities, and personal growth initiatives can enhance student well-being.

Keywords: Teachers-Student relationship, Campus facilities, Personal growth and Happiness.

INTRODUCTION

Student life is one of the most memorable and transformative periods in a person's life. During this time, individual can develop their personality, identify his or her identity and develop a sense of confidence. During this period student face various academic and social pressures, such as tight deadlines, exam preparation, maintaining high grades, peer relationships, and managing extracurricular activities, which they respond to these circumstances reflect their personality.

The availability of campus support services like academic advising, counseling, career services, and extracurricular activities plays an important role in helping students in managing these pressures and improve academic potentials. (Perez- Encinas & Ammigan, 2016) and these services not only contribute to students' success in their academic but also impact their long-term career plans and success (Lenz-Rashid, 2018).

The student's expectation and demands of the education community are rapidly changing. Large-scale European studies show that satisfied students are more capable of entering and competing in the global workplace. Therefore, student satisfaction matters before and after graduation and affects the current and future quality of life (Vaatstra & De Vries, 2007).

Many studies relieved that quality of education, cost of education, social support, nature of learning environment, facilities etc., influence student satisfaction. Now a day's educational institutions are playing a very important role in facilitating a student wellbeing by introducing a various factor that enhance students' wellbeing. Therefore, it is important to understand the institutional support system in developing student wellbeing.

Various Institution Support System contributing to student well-being are: -

1. **Mental Health Services:** Offering counselling, therapy, and mental health support services within the institution helps students manage stress, anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues.
2. **Accessibility Services:** Providing accommodations for students with disabilities ensures equal access to education. This includes physical accommodations, technological aids, and academic adjustments.
3. **Healthcare Facilities:** Access to healthcare services, including clinics or health centers on campus, ensures students have access to medical care, vaccinations, and health education.
4. **Financial Aid and Support:** Institutions offering scholarships, grants, and financial aid programs alleviate financial stress on students, enabling them to focus on their studies and overall wellbeing.
5. **Academic Support Services:** Tutoring, study groups, academic advisors, and workshops assist students in their educational journey, reducing academic stress and enhancing learning outcomes.
6. **Career Counselling and Development:** Guidance on career paths, internships, job placements, and resume-building workshops helps students prepare for life after graduation, reducing uncertainty and stress.
7. **Diversity and Inclusion Programs:** Creating a supportive environment through diversity initiatives, cultural awareness programs, and inclusivity workshops fosters a sense of belonging for all students.
8. **Wellness Programs:** Physical activities, mindfulness sessions, fitness centers, and healthy lifestyle programs contribute to students' physical wellbeing, reducing stress and promoting healthy habits.
9. **Community and Social Support:** Encouraging community engagement, clubs, student organizations, and events fosters social connections, reducing feelings of isolation and loneliness.

10. Technology Support Services: Access to reliable technological resources, IT support, and digital literacy programs ensures students can effectively engage in online learning and utilize digital tools for their studies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Several recent studies highlight the importance of educational support in nurturing student support.

1. (Scholz, Taylor, Callaghan, & Strelan, 2024) explored the efficacy of mental health and well-being education initiatives in secondary schools using triangulation of student and teacher perspectives. They have used semi-structured interviews with students and staff from four different secondary schools, using convenience and purposive sampling methods. The result revealed that both staff and students are similar when it comes to their opinions about the efficacy of mental health and wellbeing education in secondary schools. Both staff and students believe that schools need to commit to staff training, cultivate interpersonal connections, and make wellbeing education for adolescents more engaging.
2. Saxer, Schnell, Mori, and Hascher (2024), examined the role of teacher-student relationships and student-student relationships in the well-being of secondary school students in Switzerland, using mediation regression analysis to uncover how these relationships affect different dimensions of student well-being. It discusses the importance of positive relationships between students and teachers and peer relationships for academic, social, and emotional development. The study finds that both relationships are related to student well-being, but associations differ for different dimensions of well-being and for students with different individual factors.
3. Gebregergis, Kovács, and Csukonyi (2023) The study conducted a quantitative cross-sectional study to examine the extent to which psychological capital predicts psychological wellbeing and student engagement, mediated through academic stress among Eritrean higher education institutions. PsyCap includes elements like hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism, which are crucial for students' mental health and academic success. The study utilized self-report questionnaires and found that students with psychological capital show better positive psychological functioning and were

more engaged in learning and students experiencing higher levels of academic stress tended to have poorer psychological wellbeing.

4. Mangestuti, Mulyadi, Wahyuni, Aziz, and Qudzy (2022) emphasized the importance of student well-being for academic, socio-emotional, and health development. The study used observation and interviews with school staff to analyze the success of child-friendly school's programs. The research focused on learning patterns in schools, communication patterns between school members, and support for infrastructure owned by schools in developing student well-being. The study concludes that development towards Child-Friendly education is successful in improving student well-being.
5. Byrne, McGuinness, and Carthy (2022), conducted to measure how teachers feel about promoting the wellbeing of their students and administered the Attitudes Toward Wellbeing Promotion (ATWP) scale to 324 post-primary educators in Ireland. They found that, overall, educators seem to be positively disposed toward the promotion of student wellbeing. The highest levels of positivity were observed among female educators, particularly those working in all-girls schools. The lowest levels of positivity were observed among older male educators and educators working in schools that adopt streaming and vertical education practices
6. (Hou, Chin, Slem, & Oades, 2021) discussed the concept of wellbeing literacy, which is the intentional use of wellbeing relevant vocabulary, knowledge and language skills to maintain or improve the wellbeing of oneself, others and the world. The study tested the relationship between wellbeing literacy and wellbeing/illbeing. The scale was tested on three Australian samples: students, parents, and school staff. The study provides preliminary evidence that wellbeing literacy differs from existing variables across various domains of wellbeing and illbeing. Wellbeing literacy was positively associated with wellbeing, including life satisfaction, emotional wellbeing, psychological wellbeing, and social wellbeing. Results also showed wellbeing literacy was negatively associated with illbeing, including depression, anxiety, stress, and loneliness. Wellbeing literacy was empirically separable from other wellbeing and illbeing related scales, loading on its own factor, and explained additive variance in wellbeing and illbeing after controlling for emotion regulation and resilience. The study developed the Wellbeing Literacy 6-item (Well-Lit 6) scale to assess this concept within educational settings.
7. (Posselt, 2021) The purpose of the paper was to synthesize current knowledge about cultural, organizational, and environmental factors in higher education that are known

to support or inhibit the wellbeing of graduate students. It also focused to identify opportunities for administrators, program directors, faculty members, and other support staff to link mentoring and professional development practices with the promotion of wellbeing among graduate students. The paper also offers recommendations for colleges and universities to facilitate learning environments where students can succeed. The research base highlights emotional health at individual level directly contribute to physical health, healthy communities support student agency and self-determination, provide validation, support and role model at group dynamic. He directed for empirical research to get clarity about specific culture, organizational and environmental factor that operates as barriers and levels of well-being.

8. (Leshner & Scherer, 2021) report emphasized the importance of student wellbeing for academic success, giving importance on mental health, substance use and students. They found that emotional wellbeing in student is very important factor in student success. They also found that there is an increasing level of mental illness and substance use and other form of emotional distress among the students. The report emphasizes the need for innovative strategies to address these challenges, including better integration of mental health services and more comprehensive support for student wellbeing¹.It offers recommendations for improving the delivery of mental health, wellness, and substance use services in higher education institutions.
9. El-Sayed (2020), thesis exposed how teachers can improve students' wellbeing in an online setting via relationship-building practices focusing on middle school students in a fully virtual school, through classroom meeting and individual meeting. The PERMAH model of wellbeing was chosen by the researcher for the study, which stands for Positive emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, Accomplishment, and Health. Data was collected through online surveys, student interviews, and observations. The main outcome of the study was that relationship-building practices, specifically class meetings, had a significant positive impact on student wellbeing. The study also highlighted the limitations of individual meetings and emphasized the importance of proper observation techniques for valid data. The findings provided new insights into the benefits of class meetings in improving student wellbeing, supporting current literature on the topic
10. Schwab and Alnahdi (2020), The article focusses on examining three variables, namely students' school well-being, social inclusion, and academic self-concept from the perspective of both teachers and students. The main aim of the study is to investigate

the construct validity of teachers' version of the Perception of Inclusion Questionnaire (PIQ) and to see whether or not it is meaningful to include the perspective of a second teacher. Data from 151 students (86 male and 65 female students) was used in the study for the PIQ ratings. The results for psychometric properties show that the students' as well as the teachers' version of the PIQ is suitable for secondary school students. The confirmatory factor analyses demonstrated good model fit for the three-dimensional factorial structure. However, student and teacher perspectives often differ, highlighting the value of combining them.

11. (Aulia, Hastjarjo, Setiyawati, & Patria, 2020) The review highlights various definitions of student well-being, including mental health, hedonistic (pleasure-based), and eudaimonic (meaning-based) approaches. It discusses different methods used to measure student well-being, focusing on aspects like positive emotions, school satisfaction, negative emotions, social relationships, and engagement with school. The study concludes that student well-being is constructed from dominant positive emotions, satisfaction with school, minimal negative emotions, strong social relationships, and high engagement levels¹.
12. (Poots & Cassidy, 2020) The paper explores the relationship between academic expectations, self-compassion, psychological capital, social support and student well-being. This study employed quantitative methods, using surveys and questionnaires to collect data from students. The study found that self-compassion, psychological capital, and social support can help reduce the negative impact of academic stress on students' well-being. This research highlights the importance of fostering self-compassion, psychological capital, and social support to improve student well-being in the face of academic pressures. Self-compassion, psychological capital, and social support mediate the relationship between academic stress and wellbeing.
13. (Baik, Larcombe, & Brooker, 2019) paper reports on "what can be done to improve student well-being?". They studied the 7 dimensions on "Academic teachers and teacher's practices, student services and support, environment, culture and communication, course design, program administration, student societies activities and assessment".
14. (Alsubaie, H., R., & L., 2019) The paper discusses the increasing prevalence of mental health problems in university students, attributing it to academic, financial, and social stressors. Social support from family and friends was a significant predictor of depressive symptoms and quality of life, with a significant negative correlation between

all sources of social support and depressive symptoms, and a strong positive correlation between the social support subscales and the quality of life domains. The paper suggests research gaps in investigating the association between social support and quality of life in university students, examining the impact of sources of social support on both depressive symptoms and quality of life, and conducting studies that are representative of the broader student population.

15. Thesis aimed to explore the relationship of classroom support variables (teacher support, classroom support and Teacher-student relation) and student well-being. The study revealed that classroom support like classroom emotional and instrumental support and teachers emotional support are the predicator of students wellbeing. It also highlighted the importance of creating a caring classroom where care is demonstrated and acknowledge. He directed for future research on qualitative report on how teachers create supportive classroom and demonstrate care towards students. (Wingate , 2018)
16. (Powell,, Graham, Fitzgerald, & Thomas, 2018) research paper aimed at understanding the well-being in schools. They found that students view well-being as “being”, “having” and “doing” and identified the relationship with self, friends, teachers, peers and other. They directed to have a future study on school policies, practices to enhance well-being.
17. (Riekie, 2016) thesis aimed at exploring the influence of school climate on student development like student well-being, moral identity and resilience and its interrelationship. The study revealed that school climate dimensions have a signification impact on student development in promotes multidimensional goals like adjustments, attitudes, student’s engagement and improved academic achievement.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In today's fast-paced academic environment, the well-being of students plays a pivotal role in shaping their overall success and experience. Despite the availability of institution support system like academic support, career counselling, social support, extracurricular activities, technology support, physical and economic support, there are indications that certain student demographics face challenges in accessing those support. In the light of these issues, this research on the topic “Impact of Relationship with teachers, Campus Facilities and Personal Growth on Students Happiness at Campus”, tries to bridge these knowledge and population gaps and know any relationship exists between relationship with teachers, personal growth, campus climate and happiness and students.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To know whether there exist a good relationship between teachers and students
- To know whether students are happy with the campus climate and personal growth in the campus
- To analyse whether relationship with teachers, personal growth and campus climate is having correlation with student's happiness in the campus.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design: Descriptive research design – helps in providing a detailed and accurate picture of the current state of institution support systems and its impact on student wellbeing.

Participants: sampling method - Stratified random sampling will employ to ensure representation across various student demographics, including gender and academic disciplines.

Sample Size: sample size is 100

Data collection: Survey: Both Primary and Secondary data will be used to collect data. Primary data like Questionnaire, interview will be used.

Secondary data: Institution Websites

Data analysis: Regression, T-test, ANOVA and Correlation analysis is used to test the hypothesis.

HYPOTHESES

H1: There is no significant correlation between happiness and relationship with teachers, personal growth, and campus climate.

H2: There is no significant relationship between Male and Female towards happiness in the campus life.

H3: Personal Growth, Campus Climate, and Relationships do not have a statistically significant impact on Happiness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

H1: There is no significant correlation between happiness and relationship with teachers, personal growth, and campus climate.

Table No. 1.: Correlation table

	Happiness	Relationship with Teachers	Campus Climate	Personal Growth
Happiness	1.0000	0.9071	0.9036	0.9320
Relationship with Teachers	0.9071	1.0000	0.8997	0.9146
Campus Climate	0.9036	0.8997	1.0000	0.9250
Personal Growth	0.9320	0.9146	0.9250	1.0000

(JMP Analysis)

From the analysis, we find that happiness is strongly correlated with relationship, facility, and growth, as indicated by the correlation values in the table. Correlation between Happiness and Relationship with Teacher is 0.9071, with Campus Climate is 0.9036 and Personal Growth is 0.932. so, we reject the null hypothesis. Among the variable we can observe that Happiness has the strongest correlation with Growth with 0.932.

H2: There is no significant relationship between Male and Female towards happiness in the campus life.

Table No. 2.: Anova table

Source	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F Ratio	Prob > F
Gender	1	0.271690	0.271690	0.4683	0.4954
Error	101	58.602097	0.580219		
C. Total	102	58.873786			

(JMP Analysis)

From the above table we can conclude that there is no statistically significant difference in happiness between Male and Female, where p value is greater than 0.05, the result shows that no significant difference in happiness between gender. So, we fail to reject null hypothesis.

which tells that gender dose not play any impact on happiness, both have similar levels of happiness.

H3: Personal Growth, Campus Climate, and Relationships do not have a statistically significant impact on Happiness.

Graph No. 1.: Regression analysis

As per result, the p-value of 0.001, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between the variables (Happiness, Relationship with Teacher, Campus Climate and Personal Growth). This means that changes in the factors of Relationship with Teacher, Campus Climate and Personal Growth are likely to have a noticeable effect on Happiness, either increasing or decreasing it.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION.

From the analysis, it is found that Happiness is the strongly influenced with Relationship with Teacher, Campus Climate and Personal Growth, where gender doesn't have significantly affect happiness level. It's also found that enhancing Personal Growth, campus climate, teachers-student relationship can improve student happiness. The findings suggest that institutions that give importance to these factors can enhance overall student well-being, leading to greater academic satisfaction and success. So to enhance these factors, institutions should implement some mentorship program to faculty members and provide training on student engagement and foster open communication. Improving campus climate like facilities, regular student feedback, more extracurricular activities, encouraging peer collaboration, counselling and stress management workshop. By adopting these strategies, Education institutions can create a good support system that enhances student happiness, leading to greater academic success and overall well-being.

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